

D4.2 Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication Strategy (DECS) Master Plan - final

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- 1 PU = Public
 PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)
 RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)
 CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

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Summary

BIOTraCes focusses on the underlying drivers of biodiversity loss by identifying the structural factors (policies, institutions, and powerful vested interests) at the root of this loss. As these factors are related to associated values and knowledge systems that support unsustainable practices and behaviours within society, the project aims to identify these aspects as well.

The project takes a collaborative approach with local initiatives to facilitate dialogue about structural factors and to bridge differing values related to biodiversity across stakeholders. This process is essential to ensure fair and legitimate outcomes for both people and nature.

The ultimate project goal is to co-produce transformative options and pathways for sustainability that are effective, equitable and just. This will result in a Theory of Transformative Change and related tools for policy making in different sectors, beyond the lifetime of the project.

The Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication Strategy (DECS) Master Plan for Work package 4 (WP4) "Impact Creation" outlines a comprehensive approach to effectively communicate project findings, engage stakeholders, and ensure that the project's outcomes have a lasting impact on biodiversity-related transformative change. The plan covers a wide range of activities, from communication training and content creation to monitoring and exploitation strategies, all aimed at achieving the project's objectives and fostering positive change in society, policy, and science. The multifaceted approach will maximise the reach and influence of the project, ultimately contributing to the success and societal benefits.

In M12 a first version of the DECS Masterplan was published. This report is an update of the DECS Master Plan in M30 of the project. Based on insights gained and results produced, the report presents the updated strategy for the remainder of the project's duration.

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1 Introduction

1.1 About BIOTraCes

BIOTraCes aims at co-producing relevant knowledge to develop approaches and strategies that contribute to transformative changes. Those are necessary to preserve and restore biodiversity in Europe. By developing a Theory of Transformative Change (ToTC), the project will enhance the understanding of the fundamental roles played by, and connections among, values, power, and behaviour. Thus, it will address the underlying (indirect) drivers of biodiversity decline.

This objective will be achieved by building upon the principles of pluralising, empowering, politicising and embedding (Figure 1). In addition, BIOTraCes will develop capacities for innovation and foster transformative (i.e., adaptive, plural and equitable) governance approaches to achieve just and nature-positive societies.

Putting its principles into action, the consortium engages directly with transformative initiatives in four biodiversity-critical sectors across Europe (Figure 1). Actions for transformation are based on, and strengthened by, transdisciplinary approaches. Therefore, the project devises nine case studies that represent culturally, socially, economically, politically and religiously diverse contexts and landscapes. Marginalised perspectives, values, identities and groups are also involved. These include local and indigenous communities, women, non-white, gender+, immigrants, ethnic, economically and socially disadvantaged (age) groups. BIOTraCes activities include forging a multilevel network of policy makers, businesses, civil-society organisations and other stakeholders to communicate and disseminate the knowledge that we co-produce.

The project will deliver actionable knowledge and practical tools for initiating, accelerating and upscaling just transformative changes towards nature-positive societies. For this, in addition to a thoroughly designed project structure, the consortium has also established an Influencer and Stakeholder Board since M11. This Board further enhances the acquired knowledge and insights in transformative biodiversity innovations, their (sectorial) surroundings, policy networks (e.g., European Commission i.r.t. Green Deal, Farm to Fork and Biodiversity Strategy) and science-policy interfaces (e.g. IPBES, IPCC).

Figure 1. BIOTraCes images: Left: Tree with the project's 4 principles; Right: The four high impact sectors which the project's research and case studies focus on.

The present document is part of **Work Package 4 (WP4)**, which focuses on the **dissemination, communication, and exploitation** activities of the BIOTraCes project. The approach is structured across four key tasks:

1. Creation of a Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Strategy (DECS), led by ESCI (Task 4.1), which includes:
 - a. Definition of the target audiences and outline of measures for dissemination and communication, as described in this document.
 - b. Providing internal communication training to consortium partners, aiming to enhance the quality and consistency of communication and dissemination efforts across the project.
2. Dissemination, engagement, clustering, and networking activities, coordinated by UT (Task 4.2), including:
 - a. Publishing scientific articles and attending conferences and events.
 - b. Establishing dialogue with major science-policy bodies.
 - c. Producing of policy briefs, in collaboration with WP3 leader.
 - d. Final regional events in the locations of our all 9 cases.
 - e. A final international conference in the last three months of the project.
3. Communication activities including visual identity, templates, website, social media, and journalistic, audio-visual and promotional content. These actions, plus the dissemination actions will be monitored by ESCI. (Task 4.3)
4. Exploitation strategy, developed in the Exploitation Roadmap and Intellectual Property (IP) Management Plan, led by WR (Task 4.4), which aims to maximise the long-term use and impact of the project's Key Exploitable Results (KERs).

1.2 Deliverable purpose and scope

This Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication strategy (DECS) plan has been developed by ESCI and WR. The document outlines the planned actions to disseminate and exploit the project's results during the second phase of BIOTraCes, along with the supporting communication activities, with **a sharper focus on targeted dissemination and exploitation of results, supported by tailored communication activities**.

Building on D4.1 and in response to feedback the mid-term review (RP1), further efforts have been made to clarify the goals, define target audiences more precisely, and tailor dissemination and communication channels accordingly.

As the project enters its final stages, key messages (Section 1.4) have been updated to reflect this refined focus, and their relevance to specific audiences is outlined (Section 1.5). Efforts focus more explicitly on **stakeholder groups, including societal partners and case study-level stakeholders**. The strategy is underpinned by ongoing stakeholder and policy actor mapping at the local and global levels, to inform more effective delivery and support on key messages on transformative change for biodiversity.

The overarching goal of this strategy is to optimise the impact of the Theory of Transformative Change and to disseminate the related insights for policymaking in different sectors to among other science policy interface bodies, beyond the lifecycle of the project.

The DECS is a living document that has evolved with the project and the generated interest of the target groups. It provides a roadmap for the dissemination, exploitation, and communication (D, E, and C) activities of the project. To guide these efforts, four overarching **impact goals** have been defined (Table 1).

Table 1 The main goals of the BIOTraCes’ impact strategy.

Goal	Description
1	Raise awareness and inform the various societal, policy-related, scientific and private sector target groups about the project and its results.
2	Engage with enabling societal actors on the project results and proposed policy instruments to initiate and (up)scale innovative biodiversity-related transformative change processes in society, policy and science.
3	Transfer detailed, targeted and co-produced knowledge. This includes information on best practices, analytical results, methodological developments as well as collaborative and action-research approaches.
4	Develop an exploitation plan for further research and implementation of the policy recommendations beyond the project’s lifecycle. This will ensure that BIOTraCes will have a long-lasting impact.

1.3 Overview

To accomplish the set goals for communication, dissemination and exploitation, strategies are planned with a varied array of activities and different means for evaluating the implemented actions. They are summarised in Table 2. An overview of the interlinkages of the impact strategies is provided in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Overview of the BIOTraCes Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication strategy for impact creation

Table 2 Overview of the BIOTraCes Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication activities

	Dissemination	Exploitation	Communication
Description	The project’s goals and results will be disseminated through scientific journals, at academic and industrial events, and via publications for farmers and policymakers. Joint activities with other research projects are anticipated to maximise each other’s impact. These activities will be evaluated via journal impact factors or feedback forms, among other things.	The exploitation strategy will be based on a refined list of Key Exploitable Results (KERs), their target groups, potential users and early adopters. Furthermore, the Intellectual Property (IP) management plan will be elaborated. Through monitoring the policy landscape and implementing exploitation workshops, the project will refine and complete its exploitation strategy based on the project’s progress.	For an efficient communication strategy, target audiences (see 5. Target Groups) and key messages (see 4. Key Messages), as well as suitable communication channels, are defined (see 8.3. Communication Channels). The success of the communication strategy will be evaluated by means of website visits and followers on social media throughout the project. Based on this evaluation, the strategy may be adapted.
Actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 15 scientific open access publications; 10 presentations at events • Collaboration and clustering with sister projects • Handbook on ToTC • Engagement activities in the region: 45+ workshops in the region (5 per case) • 2 joint events (workshop / webinars) with related projects • 2 workshops with SPI organisation • Engagement at EU level (2 workshops) • 2 policy briefs • 1 final event & Final events in the region 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Refinement of KERs list • IP management • Exploitation workshops • Defining impact pathways • Definition of follow-up collaborative projects • Upscaling inclusive strategies for transformative change • Incorporation of project’s results in education and teaching 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creation of visual identity, Creation of Project website and social media channels (Milestone 2) • Promotional content: Posters, roll-up, brochures, 11 fact sheets (9 case related, 1 ToTC, 1 SDGs for businesses), 1 page flow, 4 infographics • Audio-visual content: introduction video, final project video, nine short videos about case studies • Journalistic content: 6+ articles, 6+ quick-fire interviews, press releases with WR
Crosslinks	Certain actions will be backed up by communication activities. For instance, by breaking down complex scientific papers into comprehensive articles or infographics for civil society/policy makers.	Exploitation will be supported by dissemination and communication actions to promote the project’s KERs, and to reach out and attract potential stakeholders. Clustering Activities will also support the exploitation, as well as the input from the Influencer and Stakeholder Board.	Where possible communication content will be used for dissemination purposes. For instance, brochures may be handed out at conferences and infographics included in presentations.

1.3.1 Targeted C&D actions linked to impact pathways

ESCI and WR have been working to align specific project activities and outcomes -including communication, dissemination, and exploitation efforts - with the impact pathways of the Key Exploitable Results (KERs). For this, an overview is created in the online whiteboard program *MIRO*. For each KER, these activities are mapped against the project's objectives, expected outcomes, and intended impacts (see Figure 3 and Annex).

The goal of this exercise is twofold: to identify any remaining gaps that can still be addressed within the project timeline, for example, through strategic actions, and to encourage stronger contributions from all partners toward maximizing the project's overall impact in the upcoming period.

This is an ongoing process, which was further developed and refined during a dedicated workshop at the in-person consortium meeting in Hungary, on 15th of May. Figure 3 and the Annex summarize the current state of this strategic mapping effort, as presented to the consortium. In a plenary discussion, the overview was reviewed, and consortium members were invited to identify any gaps and reflect on the emphasis placed on sectors, scales and KERs. This was followed by smaller groups discussions, where each group focused on one KER and shared impact activities that they felt were particularly original or significant and should be added to the overview. Insights from this workshop will be included in the overview in *MIRO*. The updated overview will be shared with all partners, along with guidance on creating outputs aligned with the defined impact pathways.

Figure 3. Work in progress - Linking C,D,E activities to project objectives, outcomes and impacts, by ESCI & WR (further screenshots in the Annex).

1.4 Key messages

The key messages for the communication about BIOTraCes are:

1. Saving biodiversity requires significant changes in how societies and economies operate.
2. BIOTraCes will tackle the root causes of biodiversity loss by identifying the underlying drivers (including structural factors like policies, institutions, vested interests).
3. BIOTraCes will identify the structural factors and associated values and knowledge systems.

4. BIOTraCes will apply and an inclusive approach (including marginalised groups) to transform those values and knowledge systems.
5. BIOTraCes will recognise and respect diverse intersecting personalities and identities of all relevant stakeholders.
6. Through nine case studies across Europe, BIOTraCes will facilitate the dialogue about structural factors.
7. BIOTraCes will enhance the transformative potential of local innovations
8. BIOTraCes will co-produce transformative options and pathways for sustainability that are effective, equitable and just.
9. The BIOTraCes research is based on four principles: Politicising, Empowering, Pluralising, Embedding.
10. BIOTraCes will develop, implement and test a distinctive approach, the “Theory of Transformative Change” and a handbook.
11. BIOTraCes aims at creating a biodiversity movement in Europe

More recently, as the project has entered a more advanced phase, we have introduced two additional key messages. These highlight the project’s long-term legacy and the practical application of its research findings:

12. BIOTraCes fosters lasting networks to support sustained collaboration between researchers, policymakers, civil society, and communities — extending beyond the project’s duration.
13. BIOTraCes translates research into practical tools to inform decision-making at all levels.

Alongside these overarching messages, we have also placed greater emphasis on communicating the specificities of each case study: the actors involved, the challenges encountered, and the strategies developed and their impacts. Illustrating the biodiversity innovations (cases) contributes to making Transformative Change more grounded, tangible and manifest.

Not all messages are equally relevant for all target groups. Each target group will be approached based on their interest (see Table 3).

1.5 Target groups

As a multidisciplinary project, BIOTraCes is of interest to several target groups. Our communication and dissemination actions aim to reach six main target groups (Table 3). Additionally, media and journalist will be targeted to disseminate and multiply the results and insights from the BIOTraCes project.

Table 3. Overview of the BIOTraCes Target Groups and the associated outcomes and impacts

Target Audience	Members	Messages
T1 Enabling players	Civil society, government, education institutions, financing and business leaders	1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,11,12,13
T2 Civil society: both locally and globally	Grassroot organizations, NGOs, organisations. Including (local) transformative biodiversity initiatives	1,4,5,7,8,10,11,12,13

T3 Science policy interfaces	IPBES, IPCC, CBD, IUCN	1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10
T4 Policy networks	European Commission, policy makers, national and European authorities, regulators	1,3,6,8,11,12,13
T5 Scientific community	Researchers and academics, students, biodiversity experts, transformative change experts	1,2,3,4,8,9,10
T6 Biodiversity and Transformative research across Europe	Related (EU-funded) projects, BISE, Knowledge Centre for Biodiversity, BiodivERsA, Oppla, NetworkNature	1,2,6,7,8,9,10,12,13

Efforts to reach these target groups will be continued in the second half of the project and will be more and more focused on exploitation-oriented dissemination (impact Goal 3 and 4, Table 1), thus supporting long-term impact of the project's results. Reaching T1, T3, and T4 is increasingly important in the next phase of the project, as science policy bodies and policy makers are key actors to reach the outcomes and impacts of BIOTraCes.

2 Dissemination Strategy

To ensure the success and visibility of BIOTraCes during and beyond its lifetime, effective dissemination and stakeholder engagement are essential. Clustering and networking activities will amplify the project's messages and contribute to broader biodiversity efforts.

The BIOTraCes project will continue to identify and assess the most effective dissemination activities, to ensure project findings reach a wide audience in impactful ways. Both dissemination and exploitation activities will continuously be aligned with the needs, capacities, and networks of each consortium member. As a Research & Innovation Action (RIA), BIOTraCes partners will keep on dedicating efforts into publishing peer-reviewed articles in AO scientific journals and presenting in high impact index conference.

Special focus has will continuously be paid to knowledge exchange and to the organisation of joint dissemination activities with other projects on transformative change related to biodiversity under the destination of this call, to the European partnership on biodiversity and the Science Service and to related projects and platforms like the Biodiversity Information System for Europe (BISE), the Knowledge Centre of Biodiversity, BIODIVERSA+, Oppla, and NetworkNature.

Finally, the consortium's expertise in stakeholder engagement will be leveraged through workshops and events held across the project's case study countries, ensuring diverse perspectives are included.

Error! Reference source not found. shows a preliminary list of dissemination activities foreseen during the project.

Approval Requirements

According to the GA annex 5, page 10/11, all partners are required to give at least 15 days advance notice to the other beneficiaries (unless agreed otherwise), together with sufficient information on the results they plan to disseminate.

2.1 Clustering and Networking Activities

2.1.1 Sister projects

There is growing agreement on the need for transformative change to address global challenges, such as biodiversity loss. However, there is less agreement about what transformative change entails and how it can be achieved. To address these knowledge gaps, the Horizon Europe Work Programme has funded 18 Horizon Europe-funded projects with a core focus on enabling transformative change for biodiversity (Table 4).

Table 4. Sister projects of BIOTraCeS

Project
<p><u>BAMBOO</u> The tools available to policymakers, retailers and other stakeholders for assessing the impacts of land and sea trade on biodiversity are limited and incomplete. By focusing on non-food biomass, BAMBOO aims to develop a set of freely available models to quantify biodiversity impacts. To do so, it will use four indicators: species richness, mean species abundance, functional diversity and ecosystem services.</p>
<p><u>BIONEXT</u> The project produces new evidence to better understand biodiversity loss and demonstrates how biodiversity underpins every aspect of life; the water we drink, the food we eat, and our health. To secure and protect these values, the project demands transformative change: BIONEXT's goal is a sustainable society, where links between biodiversity, water, food, energy, transport, climate, and health are acknowledged and nature and biodiversity are a part of everyday choices and policymaking.</p>
<p><u>BIOTRAILS</u> BIOTRAILS aims to generate knowledge and tools that will inspire and accelerate biodiversity relevant transformative change by: Building the understanding of the complex interrelations in the Climate-Biodiversity-Society nexus and between indirect drivers of changes; Co-designing interventions in policy, urban consumption, and corporate policies, for activating alternative pathways toward a just and sustainable future.</p>
<p><u>BioValue</u> BioValue focuses on the biodiversity loss due to land use and land cover changes. and intends to contribute to invert this trend and explore the transformative potential of spatial policy and planning. To do so, researchers will articulate spatial planning and management instruments with environmental assessment and financing instruments. The project will also considering the key steps of the mitigation hierarchy (avoid, minimise and offset) to stimulate the transformative potential of spatial planning through multi-level and multi-sectoral policies and strategies.</p>
<p><u>COEVOLVERS</u> COEVOLVERS investigates how marginal and vulnerable groups, as well as non-human actors can benefit from NbS. The project emphasises the role of NbS at the interface of technological and biological domains, proposing a new view for NbS design.</p>
<p><u>CLEVER</u> CLEVER will identify new leverage points for sustainable transformation. Applying a novel holistic approach, the project will quantify biodiversity and other impacts of trade in major raw and processed non-food biomass value chains. At the system level, CLEVER will improve our understanding of leakage effects in the non-food biomass trade system. At the value chain level, it will engage with producers, traders, retailers, civil society, and policymakers to identify leverage points for transformative change at corporate and institutional levels.</p>
<p><u>DAISY</u> The DAISY project aims to examine various intervention processes that address biodiversity loss and equity, ultimately providing specific policy recommendations. It will investigate current innovations and identify emerging ones in the agri-food, energy, education, and urban and regional development sectors.</p>
<p><u>GoDigiBioS</u> GoDigiBioS project aims to promote positive changes in biodiversity using new digital and emerging technologies to help reverse this decline. The project will provide a comprehensive understanding of the connections between biodiversity, social and economic well-being, and technological development.</p>
<p><u>GoNaturePositive</u> GoNaturePositive champions NbS and nature-based enterprises to redefine our economic landscape.</p>

<p><u>NATURESCAPES</u> NATURESCAPES aims to understand how NbS across interconnected urban, rural, and coastal landscapes can benefit diverse communities facing socio-economic challenges, inequity, and risk, focusing on case studies in Europe, Latin America, the US, and the Caribbean.</p>
<p><u>PLANET4B</u> PLANET4B is a transdisciplinary research project, aiming to understand and influence decision making affecting biodiversity. We rely on biodiversity for our very existence – it provides us with the basic ecosystem services that allow us to survive and thrive. Yet human lives and the biosphere itself are under threat due to the loss of biodiversity occurring at a global scale, and at an accelerating pace. Despite the mounting scientific evidence on the importance of biodiversity, it still takes a back seat to political and other agendas. Through action-orientated and participatory research PLANET4B will collect and analyse theories, methods and good practices to bridge the gaps in knowledge and effective decision making.</p>
<p><u>PRO-COAST</u> PRO-COAST seeks to inspire and empower local communities and civil society to support the restoration and maintenance of European coastal ecosystems, and thus to involve local actors more actively in environmental governance.</p>
<p><u>RAINFOREST</u> Contribute to enabling, upscaling and accelerating transformative change to reduce biodiversity impact of food and biomass value chains. The EU-funded RAINFOREST project will use a combination of integrated assessment modelling, input-output modelling and life cycle assessment, based on case studies addressing the nexus of agricultural production, processing and transport, retail, as well as consumer preferences and diets.</p>
<p><u>SUSTAIN</u> SUSTAIN (Strengthening Understanding and Strategies of business To Assess and Integrate Nature) brings together a multi-stakeholder and multi-disciplinary team to strengthen understanding and awareness of how all economic activities depend and impact on biodiversity.</p>
<p><u>TC4BE</u> TC4BE supports transdisciplinary research on telecoupled agrofood systems, engaging diverse stakeholders, including EU and producer country policy-makers, Indigenous Peoples and local communities. Scenarios and modelling of EU agrofood systems transformations will be complemented by analysis of EU governance, trade, legal, consumer, collective action and sustainable finance levers and social innovations.</p>
<p><u>TRANS-Lighthouses</u> TRANS-Lighthouses collects evidence on the tangible and intangible outcomes of NbS. This information is intended to help grasp the complexity of designing NbS that are socially and ecologically just.</p>
<p><u>TRANSPATH</u> TRANSPATH identifies leverage points and interventions for triggering transformative changes at consumer, producer and organisational levels. It seeks whole-of-society opportunities for achieving climate-neutrality whilst simultaneously allowing local communities and nature to flourish. Policy packages and other interventions are designed, to enable the emergence of leverage points at different scales of action. These interventions consider the synergies and trade-offs of actions across multiple people and places, and the role of incentives and political barriers to implementation. Diverse contexts in Eastern and Western Europe, Africa and Latin America, to engage with those who affect and are affected by trade regimes and associated 'greening' mechanisms.</p>

The European Research Executive Agency (REA) has requested that these 'sister projects' include collaborative activities in their workplan to better harness the synergies and common areas of work in the contexts of transformative change for biodiversity, to maximise the impact and exploitation of results of the projects and facilitate feedback to policy.

There are three working groups to encourage collaboration among sister projects: *WG1 Biodiversity Nexus*, *WG2 Production, consumption and global trade*; *WG3 Values, norms, justice*. Furthermore, the communication managers of all sister projects meet in specific transformative change cluster communication meetings on a bi-monthly basis.

Moreover, there is close cooperation with other relevant EU initiatives, such as **BioAgora** which is setting up the Science Service for biodiversity, and in which some BIOTraCes partners participate.

2.1.2 Achievements so far & planned joined C&D activities

The BIOTraCes sister projects from the European transformative change cluster are featured on the BIOTraCes website. Initial collaborations included featuring BIOTraCes in the newsletters of several sister projects — specifically **PLANET4B**, **CLEVER**, and **BioValue**. Further joint efforts have taken place through social media, including Transpath’s campaign that showcased each sister project and their objectives. Additional clustering activities involving all 18 sister projects are outlined in the *D5.8 Action Plan for Clustering Activities* (WR). Several targeted communication and dissemination activities with these projects have taken place/are planned, as presented in Table 5.

Table 5. Recently achieved and planned communication & dissemination activities with the sister projects

	Date	Activity	Goal / Audience	Description
2	May 8 th 2025	Webinar “The role of biodiversity in achieving SDGs: interdependencies and pathways for policy impact”	Policy makers, scientists, biodiversity experts	Organised by BIOTraCes (ESCI), joined by BIONEXT, CLEVER and BIOTRAILS, to promote our first policy brief on SDGs & biodiversity.
3	May 25 th 2025	Biodiversity Day - Social media campaign	Policy makers, scientists, general audience	Around Int. Day of biodiversity Coordinated by ESCI together with the communication managers of the "Transformative Change Cluster" including our sister projects will be a large-scale (social media) campaign around the International Day for Biological Diversity on 25 May 2025.
4	28 May	Expert-Journalist speed-dating event.	Journalists	Organized by BIOTraCes (ESCI) in collaboration CLEVER (see details in Section 2.4.3)
5	June 3 rd 2025	REA event in Brussels	Project members, policy makers	WR and ESCI will attend. Communication opportunity, highlighting the work of the transformative change cluster.
6	June 4 th and 5 th 2025	Mainstreaming Biodiversity in Policy making. Joint (final) event of several projects in Brussels	Policy makers, experts, scientists	Event organised by CLEVER, BioValue, Rainforest, Bamboo, Bedrock, BioAgora, Bionext, BIOTraCes, TRANSPATH, Planet4B and DAISY. WR is chair of a workshop, ESCI will attend the conference
7	September 2025	Policy brief on mainstreaming biodiversity in policy making (together with sister projects)	Policy makers	BIOTraCes contributes to the policy brief on mainstreaming biodiversity in policy making
	24 September 2025	Webinar on Policy recommendations for Transformative Change and Biodiversity	Policy makers, biodiversity experts	Event organised by Bionext, with BIOTraCes presenting the upcoming results of Deliverable on Transformative strategies, just governance and intersectionality"

2.2 Scientific Publications

Scientific publications are a key channel for disseminating BIOTraCes findings to researchers and the broader scientific community. The consortium aims to publish Open Access, peer-reviewed articles in high-impact journals across relevant disciplines. This is essential to ensure the project’s results reach and contribute to academic debate. Table 6 shows the scientific publications of the BIOTraCes project so far.

Table 6. Scientific publications so far

	Title	Authors	Journal name	Date
1	Multi-level finance impacts on participation, inclusion, and equity: Bricolage and Fuzziness in NextGenerationEU-funded renaturing projects	Julia Neidig, Isabelle Anguelovski, Aitor Albaina, Unai Pascual	Environmental Science & Policy	June 2024
2	Land degradation: Addressing the vulnerability of local people through the lens of transformative change	Ruxandra Malina Petrescu-Mag, Tibor Hartel, Kinga Olga Reti, Cornel Mocanu, Ioan Valentin Petrescu-Mag, Vlad Macicasan, Dacia Crina Petrescu	Heliyon	Sept 2024
3	Understanding nature's contributions to people in ancient biocultural systems through network and RLQ analysis	Andreea Nita, Kinga Olga Réti, Ruxandra Mălina, Petrescu-Mag, Dacia Crina Petrescu, Cristian Malos, László Csákány	Ecosystems and People,	Nov 2024
4	Transformative science-policy interfacing: the case of biodiversity and ecosystem services	Simo Sarkki, Juliette C. Young, Marie Vandewalle, Hannu I. Heikkinen, Roger Norum, Marie Stenseke, Carsten Nesshöver & Heidi Wittmer	Sustainability Science	Dec 2024
5	A stakeholder analysis based on project managers' perceptions: Unlocking transformative potential in Natura 2000 projects	Ruxandra Malina Petrescu-Mag, Kinga-Olga Reti, Tibor Hartel, Alexandru Sabin Bădărău, Vlad Măcicășan, Dacia Crina Petrescu	Environmental Science & Policy	Jan 2025
6	Designing for transitions through co-created artistic methods: 'gluing' affective 'rurban' encounters	Baibarac-Duignan, C., van den Eijnden, T.	World Futures Review - Futures in Transition	Jan 2025
7	Walking a Sicilian River	Paolo Gruppuso and Erika Garozzo	The Rachel Carson Center Review	Accepted, to be published in Spring 2025
8	Social justice for traditional knowledge holders will help conserve Europe's nature	Zsolt Molnár, Álvaro Fernández-Llamazares, Christoph Schunko, Irene Teixidor-Toneu, Ivan Jarić, Isabel Díaz-Reviriego, Cosmin Ivascu, Dániel Babai, László Sáfián, Pål Karlsen, Huxuan Dai, Rosemary Hill	Biological Conservation	Embargo period, open access in September 2025
9	Biodiversity conservation indicators and conflict management: Application of environmental expert-based approach in Romania.	Petrescu-Mag, R. M., Petrescu, D. C., & Azadi, H.	Journal of Cleaner Production	Embargo period, open access in February 2026

The project is placing growing emphasis on the strategic dissemination of scientific publications to a broader audience beyond the academic community. This strategy has so far included social media campaigns (via Bluesky, LinkedIn, and Instagram), uploading publications to the BIOTraCes [Zenodo](#) repository, and publishing news articles on the

project's website. The following news articles related to scientific publications have been published on the website to date:

- "New BIOTraCes research: Unlocking transformative potential in Natura 2000 projects" <https://www.biotraces.eu/new-biotraces-research-natures-contributions-to-people-in-ancient-biocultural-systems-2/> (March 2025)
- "New BIOTraCes research: Nature's contributions to people in ancient Biocultural systems" <https://www.biotraces.eu/new-biotraces-research-natures-contributions-to-people-in-ancient-biocultural-systems/> (January 2025)
- "Addressing the vulnerability of local people due to Land Degradation: New scientific article" <https://www.biotraces.eu/addressing-the-vulnerability-of-local-people-due-to-land-degradation-new-scientific-article/> (January 2025)
- "[Designing for transitions through co-created artistic methods: 'gluing' affective 'rurban' encounters](#)" (January 2025)

In line with efforts to make scientific research more accessible to the public, ESCI is developing journalistic articles based on the project's scientific publications. Two articles focusing on the results of scientific articles have been written and are in the pipeline for publication in open journals:

- [Living in Harmony with Nature: Is it possible to create a nature-positive future for Europe?, on the aims and main features of BIOTraCes, and](#)
- ["Conflicts among stakeholders affect how biodiversity projects are managed", based on the scientific article "A stakeholder analysis based on project managers' perceptions: Unlocking transformative potential in Natura 2000 projects", listed in Table 6.](#)

This strategy will become an increasing priority as we move into the final phase of the project, aiming to maximize the outreach and impact of the forthcoming scientific results.

2.3 Zenodo

A [Zenodo community for BIOTraCes](#) (Figure 4) was established in October 2023 (M10) by our partners at Mykolas Romeris University (MRU). Zenodo is an open access repository where users can upload scientific papers and other data relevant to the project. Individual partners will select a data steward who is responsible for the upload of material.

Figure 4. The BIOTraCes Zenodo community page

2.4 Conferences and events

BIOTraCes is set to deliver 10 presentations at conferences and external events by the end of the project. These presentations provide opportunities for direct engagement with a target audience of experts, stakeholders, and potential collaborators.

Strong progress has been made since the start of the project. The BIOTraCes partners have been very active, participating in the following conferences and events as speakers, rapporteurs: researchers from the University of Twente (UT), BC3, and University of Gothenburg participated and presented at the 9th, 10th and 11th IPBES plenary sessions. CES researchers took part and presented at the EMES conference, while UNICT members participated at the WINIR conference. The BIOTraCes project coordinator Rosalie van Dam attended the Earth System Governance conference and the 9th International Degrowth Conference - Planet, People, Care: It Spells Degrowth! Zsolt Molnár (CER) attended an international Herder festival and herder-scientist gathering in Hungary. Along with Esther Turnhout (UT), Zsolt Molnár attended the UN Biodiversity COP15.

The dissemination of BIOTraCes results will continue in the second half of the project, with a stronger focus on the case studies and the forthcoming handbook.

To support coordination and track participation, a detailed log of conferences and events is regularly updated and stored on the BIOTraCes MS Teams site, accessible to all project partners: https://wageningenur4.sharepoint.com/:x:/r/sites/CallBIODIV-01-09/_layouts/15/Doc.aspx?sourcedoc=%7BAD951FFB-0C95-42D2-92DA-23FE24F5E20E%7D&file=Dissemination%20Activities_monitoring.xlsx&action=default&mobileredirect=true

2.5 Dialogue with science-policy bodies and specific C&D measures to enhance policy impact

To enhance its policy impact, BIOTraCes has engaged with science-policy interface bodies and implements a range of targeted C&D activities. These efforts aim to facilitate that the project's insights on transformative change for biodiversity are translated into policy-relevant formats.

BIOTraCes has fostered dialogues in three key areas: collaboration with science-policy bodies, the development of policy briefs, and planned C&D actions specifically designed to reach policymakers.

2.5.1 Science-policy bodies

Consortium members with roles in major science-policy bodies play a vital part in conveying the project's insights to influential decision-makers. Their efforts are further supported through targeted communication and dissemination activities, which enhance the project's overall policy impact.

11th IPBES - 2024

Esther Turnhout (UT) acts as selected expert in the creation of IPBES assessments including the Land Degradation and Restoration Assessment and the Global Assessment on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. BIOTraCes partners Jeanne Nel (WR) Marie Stenseke (UGOT) have also had key roles as facilitators contributions of sessions and document drafts.

Communication and dissemination activities to emphasize their messages to IPBES and spread their insights around the 11th IPBES Plenary in December 2024 were:

- Jeanne and Esther participated in the 11th IPBES Plenary in December 2024 and featured in several journalistic articles and were featured in national (Dutch) media

(<https://www.biotraces.eu/resources/#media>), which is a good way to reach policy makers:

- Mentions in the media:
 - [EU-funded projects leading the way to transformative change for biodiversity](#) – European Research Executive Agency, 9 December 2024
 - [Huidige vorm van natuurbescherming is ontoereikend: alleen integrale aanpak kan het soortenverlies tegengaan](#) – NRC, 18 December 2024 (In Dutch)
 - [Current form of nature protection is inadequate: only an integrated approach can combat species loss](#) – TakeToNews/NRC, 18 December 2024
 - [Natuurbescherming moet radicaal anders, stelt nieuw VN-rapport. “Het is net als met slavernij: een beetje minder kan niet”](#) – Volkskrant, 18 December 2024 (In Dutch)
 - [Rapporten over biodiversiteit](#) – Vroege Vogels (Radio), 15 December 2024 (In Dutch)
 - [IPBES: Positive outcomes for people and nature are feasible, but we must act now](#) – Leiden University, 20 December 2024
- BIOTraCes website article:
 - [Interview with Prof. Esther Turnhout on key insights IPBES 11](#)

CBD COP16 - 2024

- Zsolt Molnár (CER) participated in CBD COP16 in October 2024 in Colombia, and we published a reflection article by him on our website to share his reflections and insights: <https://www.biotraces.eu/peace-with-nature-some-thoughts-about-the-cbd-cop16/>

Upcoming key science-policy meetings, in which BIOTraCes experts will participate, will be supported by targeted communication campaigns conducted by ESCI. These include:

- November 2025: *COP30*, Belém, Brazil
- October 2026: *CBD COP17* in Yerevan
- 2026: *UN International Year of Rangelands and Pastoralists*. Very important for Hungarian case, CER will participate in events.
- January 2026: *IPBES12* in the UK

Finally, BIOTraCes researchers have actively participated in past IPCC and IUCN meetings and will continue to monitor upcoming events organised by these bodies in the coming months, with a view to communicating and disseminating the project's results in these fora.

We will continue to actively communicate and disseminate the project's insights into science-policy bodies, particularly as the results become more available. Additionally, we will maintain engagement with these bodies' outreach on social media, for instance, by reflecting on and sharing their posts.

2.5.2 Policy Briefs

Translating complex research findings into accessible policy briefs is crucial for bridging the gap between academia and policymaking. Partners in WP3, in collaboration with ESCI, are working to translate the project's findings into two policy briefs. These documents distil

key insights and recommendations into concise, actionable policy guidance, making the project’s results and data more accessible and highlighting their potential impact.

In January 2025, BIOTraCes published its first policy brief (Figure 5) on the interactions between biodiversity and achieving SDGs. which was also This publication was supported by a targeted social media campaign and uploaded to Zenodo, and highlighted in a news article on the project’s website: [BIOTraCes Policy Brief](#).

To further disseminate this work to policymakers, ESCI organized a webinar on May 8, titled "The Role of Biodiversity in Achieving SDGs: Interdependencies and Pathways for Policy Impact," where the policy brief was presented. BIOTraCes partnered with sister projects BIONEXT, CLEVER, and BIOTRAILS to create an interactive program that attracted an audience of highly engaged 43 participants. To increase the reach of the session, an edited version of the webinar will be made available to all on ESCI ’s Youtube channel, with snippets and quotations highlighted in social media.

Figure 5. Screenshots from BIOTraCes first policy brief "Biodiversity Interdependencies of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)"

The same strategy will be followed for a second and upcoming policy brief, to be released in the Autumn 2025, on Mainstreaming biodiversity in EU policy making.

This policy brief will be about 4 or 5 pages long, written in a concise, direct language for an interested but non-expert audience, and drafted in conjunction with 4 sister projects. A draft has already been elaborated and shared among interested parties. The draft will be discussed in detail in the upcoming meeting of sister projects taking place in Brussels on 4-5 June.

2.5.3 Planned C&D activities targeted at policy makers

To enhance the project's policy impact, we have already implemented an adapted targeted communication and dissemination strategy, focusing specifically on maximizing policy engagement. Key actions include:

- **C&D campaign for the first Policy Brief:** This includes a social media campaign, a dedicated article on the project's website, and the organization of a webinar on May 8 titled "The Role of Biodiversity in Achieving SDGs: Interdependencies and Pathways for Policy Impact." The webinar was accompanied by a social media campaign featuring a series of visual cards highlighting key messages from the speakers, shared as teasers in the lead-up to the event. The full recording will be posted together with an invitation to watch in BIOTraCes channels, which sister projects will repost in their respective social media channels.
- **Journalistic Opinion article featuring key insights:** ESCI has finalised a feature article with Esther Turnhout (UT) and Jeanne Nel (WR), both active in IPBES. This article highlights the project's key insights for policymakers and is intended for well-read publications targeting European policymakers, such as *The Parliament Magazine* and *The European Files* - outlets where ESCI has successfully published before.
- **Journalist-Expert Speed Dating Event:** ESCI is organizing a unique speed-dating event on 28 May, where journalists and researchers will meet in breakout rooms to exchange ideas and explore potential story angles. Each meeting will last 5-10 minutes before participants are rotated to meet new contacts. This format fosters beneficial connections for both parties: journalists gain new interviewees and story ideas, while researchers receive potential media coverage. As journalistic publications are widely read by policymakers, this event aims to increase BIOTraCes' visibility among key decision-makers.
- **Ongoing Engagement on Bluesky:** Since launching our Bluesky account in December 2024 (see Section 4.3 on Communication Channels), we have actively engaged with policymakers and individuals in science-policy bodies. By following and interacting with relevant stakeholders, we have gained over 200 followers, with numbers still growing. These followers - including policymakers - will regularly see updates on our project, such as the January 2025 policy brief.

2.6 Societal dialogues

Societal dialogues have been a crucial aspect of the BIOTraCes project, enabling the active participation of local actors in shaping transformative strategies for biodiversity. In each of the case studies, societal actors have been identified, and a range of engagement activities have been carried out to foster inclusive dialogue:

1. Voedselpark Amsterdam (Netherlands): Engages local residents, urban farmers, and community activists in shaping an agroecological park as a model for sustainable urban food systems.
2. Terra Sintrópica, Mértola (Portugal): Involves agroecological farmers, food network members, and co-governance actors working together to combat desertification and revitalise rural life.
3. Environmental Studies Centre, Vitoria-Gasteiz (Spain): Works with citizens, educators, urban planners, and regional authorities to co-create sustainable policies within an ecological urban framework.

4. Dealurile Târnavelor LAG (Romania): Brings together public institutions, private enterprises, NGOs, and cultural actors to promote local development, heritage, and sustainable land use.
5. Small and Medium-Sized Forest Owners (Sweden): BIOTraCes engages individual forest owners in dialogues around sustainable forest management practices and biodiversity preservation.
6. Traditional Herders (Hungary): BIOTraCes Collaborates with herders, conservationists, and ecologists to co-develop grazing practices that support biodiversity and revive traditional knowledge.
7. Simeto River Valley Agreement (Italy): Unites civil society groups, municipalities, and universities in participatory governance for territorial planning and river restoration.
8. De Beuk, Wageningen and Program nature for each other of Province Overijssel (Netherlands): Involves developing an eco-community (future residents, ecological planners, and sustainability advocates in designing an inclusive, nature-integrated housing model) and innovative program concerning nature inclusive building which has started a movement (a nature for each other-community) of institutional and societal partners.

Actors involved in societal dialogues at the local level have been presented in our website at <https://www.biotraces.eu/societal-partners/> to provide further visibility to their involvement.

2.7 Factsheets

Since the first version of the DECS, factsheets have gained importance as a key communication channel. They are designed to make scientific insights accessible and actionable for a wide range of stakeholders, including policymakers, practitioners, civil society actors, and local communities involved in or affected by the case studies.

Factsheets can be categorized into two types:

1. **Conceptual factsheets:** These provide explanations of theoretical concepts in accessible language, aimed at students, experts, and researchers.
2. **Case study & stakeholder-specific factsheets:** These are tailored to address the needs of particular societal stakeholders relevant to the project's case studies.

Serving as concise reference materials, these factsheets offer essential project information for stakeholders. They have already been - and will continue to be - distributed at conferences, workshops, and events to ensure they reach the targeted stakeholders.

ESCI, in collaboration with different partners, has produced and published 6 factsheets so far (<https://www.biotraces.eu/resources/#comms>), see examples in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Exemplary factsheets: Factsheet 3 (left) on "Bringing ToTc" to life, and Factsheet 4 (right) for Swedish forest owners (published in both Swedish and English)

These include three conceptual factsheets explaining BIOTraCes theoretical concepts in easy-to-understand language:

1. **"Empowering Biodiversity: Pioneering Research for an Inclusive and Nature-Positive Society"**
2. **"Transformative Change"**
3. **"Bringing Transformative Change to Life"**

And three case study and stakeholder-specific related factsheets:

4. **"Forest owners' perspectives on biodiversity and climate change"** (in both Swedish and English)
Targeted stakeholders: small private forest owners in Sweden
Goal: providing information on innovative forest management practices and relevant courses and information sources available. From the interviews we learned that many forest owners do not know about available courses and information sources.
Distribution: have been provided to private forest owners during workshops in March 2025.
5. **"Why Schoolyard Greening Matters"** (in both Spanish and English)
Targeted stakeholders: parents, schools, teachers, local authorities.
Goal: providing core information about the benefits of schoolyard greening, to take away frequently asked questions and doubts. Aims to close the communication gap between the various stakeholders in the case study.
6. **"Researching the Valley of the Simeto River: Water, Agriculture and Energy"** (in both Italian and English)

Targeted stakeholders: local grassroot organisations, local authorities, residents (esp. farmers) of the Simeto Valley.

Goal: informing them about the renewable energy expansion in the river valley (incl. detailed map) and call to action to contribute to mapping the energy transition in the Simeto Valley with the Italian BIOTraCes team.

Planned Factsheets:

- Italian Case Study (UNICT): Factsheets on Water and Agriculture research in the case for local stakeholders
- Romanian Case Study (UBB): Factsheet with key insights and calls to actions for authorities, tourists, and policymakers
- Hungarian Case Study (CER): Factsheets for herders and/or policy makers
- Dutch Case Study (UT): TBD
- SDG-based Indicators (MRU): Factsheet for local enterprises

2.8 Final Events

Regional Events

The consortium will organise final events in all 9 case study locations (Netherlands, Portugal, Spain, Romania, Lithuania, Sweden, Hungary, and Italy) to engage stakeholders and gather feedback. These events aim to present the project's final results, and the developed tools and approaches for transformative change.

To facilitate dialogue, round table discussions and other interactive formats will be used to gather feedback and discuss implementation opportunities. The main target audience will include societal partners, including those representing marginalised groups, as well as all other stakeholders involved in the case studies (e.g. farmers, policy makers, schools, parents, forest owners, local authorities, etc. etc.) and beyond.

Final International Conference

The concluding international conference will play a key role in sharing project outcomes and engaging with a diverse range of stakeholders. Scheduled for the last four months of the project (M44 to M48), the conference will target various stakeholders, including representatives of science-policy bodies (e.g., IPBES, IPCC), national and EU policymakers, the scientific community, universities and research centres, and businesses.

The conference will serve as a platform to showcase the impact of the developed knowledge and methods in initiating plural, ethical, equitable, and just processes. It will present the project's activities and final results, and facilitate in-depth discussions on behaviour changes and actions related to biodiversity. The event will also address the transformative changes needed to tackle the biodiversity crisis in society, policy, and the scientific community.

3 Exploitation Strategy

The aim of the work on exploitation (Task 4.4) will be to develop and deepen the initial exploitation strategies for the project's Key Exploitable Results (KERs). The exploitation strategy will towards the end of the project include a comprehensive plan for the coordinated exploitation of KERs and the management of intellectual property (IP) generated during the project. A detailed first version of the exploitation strategy will be

described in a separate deliverable, the Exploitation Roadmap and IPR midterm (D4.6) in M20. The strategy will be updated the Exploitation Roadmap and IPR final (D4.7) due in M44.

3.1 Deepening the Exploitation Strategy

BIOTraCes exploitation is based on:

- An attractive knowledge portfolio to continue enhancing the innovations after the project end;
- A description of the steps to promote the knowledge portfolio that defines the social, policy and scientific objectives of BIOTraCes.

The portfolio of results consists of a list of KERs (Table 7)

Table 7 KER and their beneficiaries and users

No	Preliminary Key Exploitable Results	Beneficiaries / users
1	Theories of Transformative Change, including values, power relations, enabling actors	Science-policy bodies (IPBES, IPCC, CBD, IUCN), EU policy makers, Scientific community, Grassroots organisations
2	A range of methods and tools for engaging and empowering a plurality of stakeholders	Science-policy bodies (IPBES, IPCC, CBD, IUCN, EU policy makers, National and regional policy makers, Civil society, Nature organisations, Cultural groups, Scientific community, local institutions
3	Demonstration and implementation of process of transformative change in 9 EU case studies	Policy makers at the regional and national level in member states of case studies
4	Just, ethical, plural, socially inclusive strategies for propelling transformative change	EU policy makers, National and regional policy makers, Civil society
5	Transdisciplinary learning community / network from local to EU level on transformative change for biodiversity	Science-policy bodies (IPBES, IPCC, CBD, IUCN), EU policy makers, Civil society, Scientific community, education institutions

The exploitation roadmap includes individual and joint efforts and related organisation of such collaborative efforts (partnership policy and governance). It will describe the consortiums plans to do further research, promote results, and influence policy after the project ends, among other things. The following steps will be taken to come to a final exploitation plan:

Analysis of Opportunities:

The task will involve a thorough analysis of opportunities for exploitation in science, policy, and society. This analysis will identify gaps in existing practices and propose areas where the project's findings can be leveraged to drive transformative change.

Planning of the next steps:

Partners will collaborate to plan the next steps for fully exploiting project results. This includes formulating proposals for continued work, establishing governance structures to facilitate joint exploitation, and creating a roadmap for ongoing partnership activities.

Organisational Structure:

Partners will define the organisational structure for joint exploitation efforts, specifying roles, responsibilities, and decision-making processes.

Promotion Activities:

Strategies for promoting the exploitation of results will be outlined in line with the communication and dissemination strategy, including engagement with stakeholders, and outreach efforts that are specifically targeted to support exploitation of the BIOTraCes results.

3.2 Intellectual Property (IP) Management

The main type of IP generated in BIOTraCes are methodologies, know-how, and tools. As a Horizon-funded research project, BIOTraCes is required to examine the possibility of protecting its results and to ensure an adequate protection both during the duration of the project and within its geographical coverage

A dedicated deliverable (D4.6) developed the approach to IP Management for BrioTraCes, to ensure the protection and responsible management of the project's related IP, and in line of with European Commission's IP Helpdesk. The IP Helpdesk defines five pillars of knowledge for this endeavour:

1. IP used in the project (access and usage rights for background knowledge);
2. IP generated by the project (ownership of results/foreground);
3. IP assessment (identifying market opportunities and protection strategies);
4. IP protection (e.g. through copyright or other legal means);
5. IP dissemination and exploitation (in research, education, commercial applications, or policy contexts).

All five pillars are considered in the IP management process and in the development of an appropriate protection strategy for the project's outputs.

Risk Assessment

Potential risks in the exploitation of project-related IP will be identified and assessed. This includes understanding the impact of these risks and anticipating corrective actions to mitigate them. As part of the assessment, a proposition of optimal IPR protection options, in line with obtained results will be developed.

4 Communication Strategy

To boost the visibility during the lifecycle of the project and beyond, ESCI has created a wide range of communication activities. The main aim of the communication activities has been to raise awareness, inform and increase visibility of the BIOTraCes project and its solutions to relevant stakeholders and the public at large. This has been done through creating meaningful content to convey accessible messages about the project's activities, its results, implications and benefits. The project will continue to do so in similar ways.

Social media channels (e.g. Instagram, Bluesky, LinkedIn, YouTube) and the BIOTraCes website have been used for wide communication. More specialised channels (e.g. special interest magazines) have aided to reach out to specialists' audiences (e.g. civil society,

policy makers, NGOs), while the local media (e.g. local newspapers, radio and TV) to reach out to society at large.

The results of the communication and dissemination actions will be published in a report on “Best practices of Communication and Dissemination Actions”, due in July 2026 (D4.4, M44). This report will highlight and describe the best communication and dissemination strategies. The reports will serve as inspiration for communication and dissemination actions to other European projects.

Approval Requirements

BIOTraCes fully complies with the requirements for communication and dissemination established in the Grant Agreement, as outlined in Annex 5 (pages 10–11). All partners are required to provide at least 15 days’ advance notice to other beneficiaries (unless agreed otherwise), along with sufficient information on the results they intend to disseminate.

Different approval procedures apply depending on the type of content. While no formal approval is needed for social media posts created by partners, other promotional and journalistic materials—such as brochures, graphics, and articles—must be submitted to the project coordinator for approval. This ensures both the accuracy of the content and the protection of any confidential information. If a specific partner’s expertise forms the basis of the content, their approval will also be sought.

Press releases prepared by individual partners are their own responsibility, but it is recommended to inform the communication manager to enable further dissemination through BIOTraCes’ social media channels. For journalistic content, only the organisations or individuals mentioned in the article will be contacted for fact-checking and approval.

4.1 Branding

BIOTraCes has been “branded” with a unique visual identity. A strong, attractive and consistent visual identity facilitates communication, dissemination and exploitation activities. In this way, it assures a design that is easily identified. Stakeholders will quickly attribute content to the project which can foster engagement and dialogue. The branding includes the project logo, a colour code and fonts. These elements have been used when creating project material.

4.1.1 Tagline, Logo, Colour Code

A tagline was created for BIOTraCes: “Connecting for Biodiversity”. This reflects two main aspects of the project: society and nature – united for boosting biodiversity. The tagline gives an idea and as such will help to attract attention from relevant stakeholders.

A simple and modern logo was developed (Figure 7). Its elements, including the feet and the leaves, reflect the two main aspects of BIOTraCes: Society and biodiversity. All versions exist with and without the tagline. The logo must not be altered or adapted, and care must be taken to not distort the dimensions. The logo is available in multiple versions including a white or transparent background or with a green background.

A set of primary colours was chosen to be primarily used for project content. These are complemented with a set of secondary colours. The green tones, reflect the biodiversity and nature. These colours can be used to convey information at different levels of importance based on the effect of the colours (Figure 7).

Figure 7. A) The BIOTraCes logo in white; B) The BIOTraCes logo in green; C) The BIOTraCes colour code

4.1.2 Fonts and Variation of English

The main font of the project is Verdana. For purposes of consistency and according to EU requirements, it is recommended to adhere to British English spelling conventions where possible.

4.1.3 Funding Acknowledgement

Communication and dissemination content must display the EU Horizon emblem and the following text as per Grant Agreement:

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

4.2 Templates

Different templates – such as this deliverable template, a report template, a PowerPoint template, and a Meeting Minutes template - were created following the visual identity of BIOTraCes for consistency and easy recognition by stakeholders. The template available in the BIOTraCes Teams-Folder. They can be used for communication, dissemination and exploitation activities as necessary (Figure 8).

Figure 8. The BIOTraCes templates: A) The PowerPoint template; B) The simple word document template; C) The meeting minutes; D) The deliverable template

4.3 Communication channels

4.3.1 Website

Since February 2023 (M3), the BIOTraCes website has been live: <https://www.biotraces.eu/>. Serving as a central "digital anchor" for the project, the website aims to achieve the goals outlined in the DECS and provide a comprehensive information hub for all relevant stakeholders. It introduces the BIOTraCes concept and showcases our nine case studies across Europe.

The website is regularly updated with project news, including reflections from conferences attended by partners, interviews (such as the 'Coffee Talks' and video interviews - see Section 4.5.3), announcements of newly published research, and journalistic articles, among other content.

The 'Results' page has been significantly updated to feature the project's first findings: <https://www.biotraces.eu/resources/>. This page includes sections for:

- Scientific Publications
- Policy Briefs

- Communication Materials (such as factsheets, infographics, flyers, roll-ups, and page flows)
- Journalistic Articles & Media Coverage
- Videos

Each section includes links to relevant content, including scientific papers, media coverage, and BIOTraCes resources like policy briefs, public deliverables, and downloadable graphics. This page will become increasingly important in the final project phase as more results are to be published.

Additionally, the website was updated with sections on our **societal partners** from the case studies: <https://www.biotraces.eu/societal-partners/>, and our **Influencer and Stakeholder Board**: <https://www.biotraces.eu/influencer-and-stakeholder-board/>.

Social media activities also complement the website, linking back to it and helping to attract visitors, thereby increasing project visibility and awareness.

In the coming period, we will continue to update the website regularly, particularly as more results are generated and upcoming BIOTraCes events will take place. The focus will shift toward exploitable outcomes, key insights for major science-policy bodies, and the project's final events.

4.3.2 Social Media

Social media is a good tool to get in contact with all relevant stakeholders and stay connected with them on a regular basis. Different social media platforms are used to spread information to relevant stakeholders and engage with them. This has already built a community of interested stakeholders and early adopters of BIOTraCes. Furthermore, it fosters interests and trust. All channels have the same account name: BIOTraCes. This allows interested stakeholders to easily find the project on different platforms. Regular posts along with dedicated social media campaigns (such as the current "Faces" campaign) will build a community of relevant stakeholders. The project website contains plugins to all social media channels, helping to attract followers. All the consortium partners are also encouraged to invite stakeholders to follow the BIOTraCes accounts, to share posts among their community and to actively post themselves about the project and their involvement.

4.3.3 LinkedIn

LinkedIn is the top online platform for professionals with more than 1 billion members in 200 countries worldwide¹. It is used to search jobs, connect to professionals, strengthen professional relationships and learn relevant career skills. It has also been a strong platform for Horizon-funded projects. The LinkedIn BIOTraCes channel (Figure 9) is active since the project's start in December 2022 (M1). Since then, it has successfully created a dedicated and active community of scientists, policy makers, grassroots organisations, students, and NGOs, consisting of 637 followers (status 23 May 2025). To attract our target groups to the LinkedIn account, news about the project is shared regularly. The account will be increasingly used in the last half of the project to disseminate results and share exploitation related content and opportunities.

4.3.4 X (formerly Twitter)

X (formerly Twitter) is an online news and social networking site. The X account @Biotraces_EU was started in M1 of the project, however due to the new X owner and related policies/algorithms on the platform, the BIOTraCes consortium has discussed a potential switch away from X and decided in favour of that strategy.

¹ LinkedIn (April 2025). <https://about.linkedin.com/>

The number of X followers steadily declined during 2024, the project had 210 followers on 16 September 2024, which reduced to 136 followers on 5 December 2024. The decline especially accelerated after the US elections in November 2024. At the start of December 2024, we decided to leave X. The BIOTraCes X account has been inactive since December 2024. A post is pinned on top of the feed to refer to our other communication channels. As a replacement, we opened a Bluesky account, because we observed the relevant science and policy communities moving there (see below). We have adapted our PowerPoint templates and website to reflect the changes with new symbols.

4.3.5 Bluesky

Bluesky is an emerging social media platform that has surpassed 27 million users and continues to grow². On December 5, 2024, BIOTraCes launched its official Bluesky account in response to a noticeable shift among scientists—particularly within the science-policy and IPBES communities—toward this platform. This migration gained momentum following the U.S. elections in November 2024.

Scientists and policymakers are among our key target audiences, and both ESCI and WR recognized the value of engaging with them on Bluesky. The account was strategically launched just ahead of the 11th IPBES Plenary to capitalize on the event’s momentum - aiming to attract followers and contribute meaningfully to the ongoing discussions by sharing insights from BIOTraCes.

As our first campaign, we ran an #IPBES11 initiative on Bluesky (simultaneously with LinkedIn), providing live updates from Prof. Esther Turnhout (University of Twente), background on IPBES, real-time highlights from the plenary, and reflections on key outcomes and perspectives.

ESCI encourages BIOTraCes researchers—as well as our sister projects—to join Bluesky. One added benefit is that Altmetric now tracks Bluesky mentions, which can serve as a measurable indicator of researchers’ outreach and engagement.

As of May 2025, the BIOTraCes Bluesky account has gained over 225 followers - already surpassing the number we had on X (formerly Twitter) - with continuing steady growth.

4.3.6 Instagram

Instagram is a photo and video sharing platform with over 2 billion active users worldwide. The Instagram account @biotracces (Figure 9) is live since the BIOTraCes project start on December 1, 2022 (M1). The content is tailored to the target audiences to ensure that it is comprehensive for non-experts. Instagram is an important platform for the project to reach specific societal stakeholders like citizens, grassroots, farmers, etc.

During the first phase of the project, the account focused on introducing BIOTraCes, its partners and activities, and raising awareness about biodiversity. In the current phase, the strategy starts to shift to presenting project outcomes: we will launch a concluding series sharing key learnings from each case study, accompanied by a visual campaign exploring the BIOTraCes principles in practice.

² Backlink (January 2024). <https://backlinko.com/bluesky-statistics>

A

B

C

D

Figure 9 The BIOTraCes online platforms: A) The project webpage; B) The LinkedIn account; C) The BlueSky account; D) The Instagram account

4.3.7 YouTube

YouTube, the world’s largest video-sharing platform, has over 2.7 billion viewers globally³. To maximize visibility and engagement, ESCI uses this platform to publish and promote video content related to the BIOTraCes project. Rather than launching a new channel from scratch, all BIOTraCes-related videos are hosted on ESCI’s established YouTube channels- "ESCI" and "ESCI – Science Talks Extended"- to benefit from ESCI’s existing subscriber base and stronger reach

This strategic approach has proven effective and will be continued. As of April 2025, the main ESCI YouTube channel has 2,570 subscribers and features 169 videos, making it a well-performing communication tool. Notable BIOTraCes videos published include the introductory video, published on July 18, 2023, and the Portuguese case study video, released on September 3, 2024 (See section 4.4).

4.4 Promotional Content

Creating promotional materials is essential for increasing the visibility and outreach of the project. For this purpose, our communication strategy includes the production of visual and audio-visuals content. The audio-visual content is a powerful medium to convey the project messages. These activities fulfil specific objectives 1-4 of this DECS. (See Section 2. Document Purpose and Scope).

³ Global Media Insight (April 2025). <https://www.globalmediainsight.com/blog/youtube-users-statistics/>

4.4.1 Infographics

Already five infographics have been produced to display complex project findings and insights into visually appealing and easy-to-understand formats. These infographics have been shared across the BIOTraCes communication channels to engage a wider audience. ESCI created the first infographic based on the already existing designs in M9. It provides an overview of the nine case studies, the “core” of the BIOTraCes action research. Also, an infographic on the High Impact Sectors has been produced. Furthermore, three infographics have been produced based on the policy brief on SDGs and Biodiversity (Figure 10): <https://www.biotraces.eu/resources/#comms>. Further infographics are being planned to easy dissemination of certain information and results of the project, among others a map of the renewable energy initiatives in the Simeto valley in the Italian case study, which will be part of the related factsheets. Infographics for the final Handbook are also foreseen.

Figure 10. Two of the three infographics based on the policy brief on SDGs and biodiversity

4.4.2 Audio Visuals

Introductory video

ESCI produced an introductory video that explains the project's objectives: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=pSHdXXCYsdK>. The video serves as an engaging and accessible entry point for stakeholders, including biodiversity innovators, universities, policy makers, and science-policy bodies. The background story features the WR case study, the planned building of an eco-community in Wageningen. The film was aired on 5 July, 2023 (M8) on the BIOTraCes social media channels, the website and the ESCI YouTube channel. The film has reached 924 views on YouTube (status May 2025), which is, compared to related projects, an excellent number. The film performed very well on LinkedIn where it reached 1.352 impressions.

Audio Visuals: Short case study videos

Every consortium partner produced a video of their case studies. These 9 videos showcased the unique challenges and solutions implemented in each case study, making the project's

work more relatable and understandable to a broader audience. The videos were produced prior to the in-person meeting in M4 and published consecutively on social media between May-August 2023.

ESCI has produced and published an additional Portuguese case study video, which was filmed during the live meeting in Portugal in 2024. It was published on September 3rd, 2024 (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=C0Fyr5aoKwk>). The film has reached 2957 views on YouTube so far (Status May 2025). An additional of 5 video interviews with key stakeholders in the Portuguese case has been published on YouTube as well.

ESCI plans to produce a case study video of two more case studies, most probably the Hungarian and Lithuanian case study, which will be produced after filming at physical meetings taking place there in 2026.

Audio Visuals: Final project video

A final video will be created to summarise the project's results in an impactful way. It will include testimonials from stakeholders, highlighting transformative biodiversity innovations (D4.5). This video will target biodiversity innovators, universities, policy makers, and science-policy bodies.

Audio Visuals: Page flow

A Pageflow was created in M10 of the project to visually communicate the project's processes and impact pathways: [BIOTraCes – Connecting for Biodiversity](#). This interactive visual tool helps stakeholders better understand the complexity of the project and its potential for transformative change. The Pageflow combines text, video, and slides in an intuitive and user-friendly format, making it easy to navigate while offering a rich, multimedia experience.

4.4.3 Supporting Promotional Materials

Flyers and posters are a great tool to further promote the project goals and results. They can be used online for social media or printed for seminars and conferences. Prior to the project start, WR has created this flyer as a comprehensive overview of the BIOTraCes project goals and principles. Additional communication materials, including a roll-up have been created for the project, to further strengthen the project's visibility and outreach (<https://www.biotraces.eu/resources/#comms>). WR has already designed a flyer prior to the official project start. These materials will be strategically distributed at events, conferences, and other relevant venues.

4.5 Journalistic Content

Creating engaging and informative journalistic content is essential for capturing the attention of stakeholders and the wider public. Thus, ESCI has and will produce high-quality journalistic content including journalistic articles and interviews and press releases. Through these actions we aim for 30.000 downloads, views, reads and impressions on different channels (online, print). These activities fulfil specific objectives 1-4 of this DECS. (See Section 2. Document Purpose and Scope).

4.5.1 Press Releases

Press releases will be written and published to announce important milestones of the project. An initial press release was published in M1 to announce the launch of the project.

4.5.2 Journalistic Articles & Media mentions

To effectively communicate project findings and insights in an accessible and engaging way, at least six professionally produced journalistic articles are planned for publication on relevant online platforms.

To date, ESCI has already published five articles (see Table 7). In addition, the project has received wider media coverage:

- BIOTraCes was featured in an *Earth.Org* article focused on innovative approaches to agriculture.
- A Spanish-language article appeared in *Capital Vitoria*.
- An Italian article was published in *Catania News*.
- The project was also highlighted in a REA article covering EU-funded initiatives on transformative change for biodiversity (see Table 7).

More articles are currently in development. ESCI is already working on two upcoming features, which are expected to be published in the next phase of the project.

1. "Living in Harmony with Nature: Is it possible to create a nature-positive future for Europe?" (working title)
A journalistic opinion article featuring Esther Turnhout (UT) and Jeanne Nel (WR), who are both active in IPBES. The article will feature the project's key insights relevant for policy makers. This article is to be published in well-read a magazine by European Policy Maker: Targeted are [The Parliament Magazine](#) and [The European Files](#), in which ESCI published successfully before.
2. "Conflicts among stakeholders affects how biodiversity projects are managed" (working title)
An article based on a scientific publication of the project ("A stakeholder analysis based on project managers' perceptions: Unlocking transformative potential in Natura 2000 projects").

4.5.3 Quick-Fire Interviews

In addition to the articles, ESCI will conduct at least six quick-fire interviews with experts from our consortium in transformative change and biodiversity. These interviews (Table 8) will provide concise and insightful perspectives on project-related topics and will be disseminated across various media channels, including partner websites, newsletters, and relevant magazines.

To date, ESCI has released one written quick-fire interview with Dr. Zsolt Molnár, a consortium member from the Ökológiai Kutatóközpont, the Hungarian Centre for Ecological Research (CER). Additionally, ESCI has conducted three quick-fire interviews with BIOTraCes project members—Rosalie van Dam, Oscar Jacobsson, and Samadhi Lipari—published under the series title "*Coffee Talks*."

The interview with Samadhi Lipari led to a successful follow-up: a journalist from a Sicilian newspaper expressed interest in conducting a further interview with her. Finally, in October 2024, ESCI published a series of six video interviews with stakeholders from the Mértola case study.

Table 7 The BIOTraCes articles and interviews

Overview Articles and Interviews			
Article or Interview	Title	Publication Date	Publication Location
Article	https://www.catanianews.it/progetto-eu-horizon-biotraces-un-team-unict-per-la-biodiversita/	May 4, 2023	Catania News
Article	May I introduce myself? I am Balint's hat!	June 27, 2023	The BIOTraCes website
Article	The hidden knowledge that could help us manage the	July 5, 2023	Inside Ecology

	biodiversity crisis		
Interview	Tapping traditional herders' wisdom to nurture biodiversity	August 5, 2023	University World News
Article	Europe's Agricultural Future May Lie in Both Innovative and Ancient Farming Practices	September 5, 2023	Earth.Org
Article	5 years of Fridays for Future: Researchers say climate strikes bring slow but sure change	September 15, 2023	Euronews.green
Interview	Coffee-Talk with Rosalie von Dam "Practice what you preach"	November 13, 2023	The BIOTraCes website
Article	Comienza la naturalización de los patios escolares de Arantzabela Ikastola y de Primaria del CPI Sansomendi IPI	January 10, 2024	Capital Vitoria (Spanish)
Article	Indigenous women's more complex idea of biodiversity	March 8, 2024	University World News
Video interview	Making a big difference – Interview with Marta Cortegano	October 1, 2024	The BIOTraCes website
Video interview	Making a big difference – Interview with Pedro Nogueira	October 8, 2024	The BIOTraCes website
Video interview	Making a big difference – Interview with António Coelho	October 15, 2024	The BIOTraCes website
Video interview	Making a big difference – Interview with Rosinda Pimenta	October 22, 2024	The BIOTraCes website
Video interview	Making a big difference – Interview with Luciane Lucas dos Santos	October 29, 2024	The BIOTraCes website
Article	EU-funded projects leading the way to transformative change for biodiversity	December 9, 2024	REA website
Reflections	Peace with nature? Some thoughts about the CBD COP16	January 8, 2025	The BIOTraCes website
Article	Behind the scenes of Terra Sintropica	November 4, 2024	Illuminem
Reflections	Linking Scientific Knowledge on Biodiversity Loss to Concrete, Hopeful Action: Insights from the 'Navigating the Anthropocene' Conference	February 10, 2025	The BIOTraCes website
Interview	Coffee-Talk with Oscar Jacobsson: Private forest owners' perspectives in Sweden	February 11, 2025	The BIOTraCes website
Interview	Coffee-Talk with Samadhi Lipari: Renewable Energy in the Simeto valley	March 17, 2025	The BIOTraCes website

4.6 Internal Communication & Communication training

Communication within the consortium is facilitated by the coordinator. When not held in person, general meetings are conducted via Microsoft Teams. Work Package (WP) and other necessary meetings are held regularly to maintain a consistent flow of information throughout the consortium. Meeting documents and recordings are shared on the Teams platform. This activity contributes to Specific Objective 1 of this DECS (see Section 2: Document Purpose and Scope).

4.6.1 Communication Training

Supporting consortium partners in effectively engaging with journalists and the media (e.g., responding to press inquiries, giving interviews, and preparing press releases) enhances awareness of BIOTraCes among key stakeholders. To this end, ESCI conducted a communication training session on journalistic fundamentals during the first in-person consortium meeting at WR in Month 4 (M4). This activity fulfils Milestone 3, as outlined in Annex B of the Grant Agreement

5 Monitoring

To ensure that communication efforts are effective and adaptable, ESCI has established robust monitoring mechanisms.

5.1 Website Analytics

A GDPR-compliant version of Google Analytics called “Metricool” is being used to track the project’s website performance. This provides detailed insights into website traffic, user behaviour, and engagement levels.

5.2 Social Media Monitoring

The BIOTraCes social media channels Instagram, Bluesky, LinkedIn, are being monitored with Falcon and Metricool. These tools track engagement metrics, such as likes, shares, comments, and follower growth. The data is used to assess the impact of social media campaigns and tailor content accordingly.

5.3 Event Surveys

Satisfaction surveys will be conducted at events, including conferences and regional gatherings. These surveys will collect feedback from participants, helping to evaluate the effectiveness of event communication and identify areas for improvement.

5.4 Reporting and Analysis

Data collected through monitoring mechanisms will be analysed regularly to evaluate the impact of communication and dissemination actions. The insights gained will be used to optimise ongoing activities, ensuring that the project reaches its target audiences effectively.

These findings will also contribute to Deliverable D4.4 Best Practices of Communication and Dissemination Actions in July 2026 (M44). Detailed monitoring data can be found on the ESCI database and BIOTraCes Teams platform.

6 Status of C&D KPIs and future plans

Several key performance indicators are included in the GA for the project’s communication and dissemination actions. They are summarised below (**Error! Reference source not found.**):

Table 8. Key communication and Dissemination KPIs and their status

KPI	Status (May 2025)	Upcoming plans
15 peer-reviewed scientific publications, reaching 400 scientists and researchers’ presentations at events, reaching 600 scientists.	9 peer-reviewed scientific articles have been published so far (See Section 2.2)	Accelerating academic publications, based on data that is being collected, analyses that are being finished and results coming in during this next project period.
2 joint events (workshops/webinars) with related projects 2 workshops with SPI organisations >100 new contacts from biodiversity	2 joint events organised by BIOTraCes (ESCI): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 8 May 2025: Webinar on “SDGs and biodiversity” 	1 webinar on policy recommendations for transformative change planned in September 2024

and transformative research and other stakeholders	<p>together with BIONEXT, BIOTRAILS and CLEVER.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 28 May 2025 "Scientist-Journalist speed dating together with CLEVER. 	
6 journalistic articles, 6 expert interviews, and press releases resulting in 30.000 downloads, views, reads and impressions on different channels (online, print)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 8 journalistic articles have been produced and published in a variety of European outlets (See Section 4.5). REA has published 1 journalistic article about BIOTraCes's and its sister projects. 8 interviews published on the BIOTraCes website (see Table 7). 3 press releases 	<p>2 journalistic articles based on relevant project developments are drafted and ready for upcoming publication and to reach specific target groups..</p> <p>Producing at least another 3 interviews with key researchers in the project, continuing the "Coffee Talk" series.</p>
11 Fact Sheets (9 case focused, 1 ToTC factsheet, 1 SDGs for businesses factsheet)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 6 Factsheets completed 	5 more factsheets in progress
4 infographics, 1 page flow	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 5 infographics produced Page flow published 	More infographics planned, among others as part of the factsheets.
Original content published on social media, resulting in >500 followers and 12,000 web visits / year, 35.000 impressions in total on social media accounts and webpage	Total 1014 followers on social media (637 on LinkedIn, 152 on Instagram, 225 on Bluesky)	Continuing our activity on social media, based on engaging campaigns and increasingly focused on results and implications for science and policy
5+ workshops per case study at local and if relevant at national level (>45 workshops in total)	In progress, is monitored by UT.	Continued implementation of local workshops.
2 policy briefs >45 engagement activities with stakeholder groups in case locations. WP3 deliverables reaching >150 policy makers on regional, national and EU level	1 policy brief published (See Section 2.5.2)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 more policy brief on Transformative Strategies (M44, D3.4) Potential policy brief together with sister projects.
80+ stakeholders at international conference – One final event with more than 80 stakeholders and final events in various regions >1,000 policymakers, governments, associations, and BIOTraCes partners	Not yet relevant	Coming-up at the end of the project

The project is on track to meet, and in some cases exceed, its communication and dissemination targets. These activities are not just about numbers: they help ensure that findings from the case studies reach the right audiences and inform wider debates on transformative change for biodiversity.

As we move forward, the focus will be on sharing results in accessible formats – Factsheets, videos, journal articles - deepening engagement with key stakeholders via local and final conferences, participation and organisation of activities with sister project, and drawing out lessons that can be applied beyond the project’s specific contexts, with the Handbook and academic articles, amongst others.

Annex

a) Overview of WP4 Deliverables

Table 9 Overview of WP4 deliverables

Del. No.	Deliverable name	WP No.	Lead beneficiary	Nature	Dissemination level	Delivery date from Annex I (project month)	Delivered Yes/No	Actual / Forecast delivery date
D4.1	Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication Strategy (DECS) masterplan midterm	WP4	ESCI	R — Document, report	PU-Public	M12	Yes	M12
D4.2	Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication Strategy (DECS) masterplan final	WP4	ESCI	R — Document, report	PU-Public	M20	Yes	M20
D4.3	Workshop reports	WP4	UT	Other	PU-Public	M44	No	M44
D4.4	Best practices of Communication and Dissemination Actions (numbers of downloads, involvement, etc.)	WP4	ESCI	DEC — Websites, patent filings, videos, etc	PU-Public	M44	No	M44

D4.5	Video with testimonies of transformative biodiversity innovations	WP4	ESCI	DEC — Websites, patent filings, videos, etc	PU-Public	M44	No	M44
D4.6	Exploitation Roadmap and IPR midterm	WP4	WR	R — Document, report	PU-Public	M20	Yes	M20
D4.7	Exploitation Roadmap and IPR final	WP4	WR	R — Document, report	PU-Public	M44	No	M44

b) Overview of WP4 Milestones

Table 10 Overview of WP4 milestones

MilestoneNo.	Milestone name	Work package No.	Lead beneficiary	Delivery date from Annex I	Achieved Yes/No	Actual / Forecast achievement date	Comments
2	Launch of our website	WP4	ESCI	M4	Yes	M3	The associated social media channels launched in M1. The website was made live in M3.
3	Communication training	WP4	ESCI	M6	Yes	M4	The communication training was performed during the live meeting in M4

c) Impact pathways: linking C,D,E activities to project objectives, outcomes and impacts (Work in progress)

KER3 (Demo and implementation of cases): Impact pathway

Short-term

Results (e.g. Deliverables (D),
Workshops (W), Comm & Diss (C&D))

KER4 (Just, ethical, plural strategies): Impact pathway

Short-term

Results (e.g. Deliverables (D), Workshops (W), Comm & Diss (C&D))

KER5 (Trans. learning community) : Impact pathway

